

29 five liters of heating oil per square meter per year, older buildings consumed about 25 liters on average [2].
30 On the other hand, the U.S. Department of Energy (DOE) is advancing in building energy performance
31 through the development and promotion of efficient, affordable, and high impact technologies, systems,
32 and practices. The long-term goal of the building technologies office of the DOE is to reduce energy usage
33 by 50%, compared to the 2010 baseline [3].

34 New technologies in buildings were introduced to improve the energy efficiency and reduce
35 energy usage in buildings, such as thermal insulation materials applied in the building envelope or phase
36 change materials (PCM) [4]. The use of PCM as storage medium for both cooling and heating applications
37 appreciably reduces the energy demand of the building sector due to the high latent heat of the PCM at low
38 temperature [5]. For this reason, the scientific community has been developing studies of PCMs building
39 applications over the past decade [6]- [14]. Although, free cooling potential showed promising capabilities
40 toward space cooling applications, it has not yet been widely commercialized and implemented in
41 residential sectors [5].

42 PCM as building materials to improve the performance of heating, ventilation and air-conditioning
43 (HVAC) systems has been implemented as an energy efficiency measure during the last decades. Rastogi
44 et al. [15] developed a selection and performance assessment of PCM for HVAC in a room house.
45 Turnpenney et al. [16] studied the reduction of air conditioning, using an innovative ventilation system using
46 PCM. Parameshwaran et al., [17] presented a research about reducing air conditioning and improve energy
47 efficiency in buildings using PCM latest generation variable volume. Sun et al., [18] conducted an economic
48 and energy analysis in a building equipped with PCM wallboards.

49 The selection of the most appropriate PCM is a crucial component for the design and development
50 of the building. Comparing candidate materials, ranking and choosing the best material, are one of the most
51 important stages in the material selection process. To accomplish the selection, efforts need to be extended
52 to identify those criteria that have a major influence in the engineering application to eliminate unsuitable
53 alternatives and select the most appropriate choice using simple and logical methods [19, 20]. The proper
54 choice of PCM depends on factors such as their physical and thermochemical properties. In this regard, it
55 has been demonstrated that the material selection process can be developed for a systematic and efficient
56 approach as multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) problem [19, 20].

57 In this direction, the application of material selection has been developed for PCM in energy
58 storage. Fernández et al., [7] conducted the selection of PCM materials for sensible thermal energy storage
59 between 150–200 °C by the CES Selector software. Additionally, in 2013, Khare et al., [8] studied the
60 selection of PCM materials to evaluate sensible heat storage between 500–750 °C by the software package
61 - Granta Design's CES Selector.

62 In contrast, simulations which assess the thermal behavior of PCM in buildings provide essential
63 information of the energy consumption and could improve the design process of the building. For this
64 purpose, several numerical models have been developed to assess the thermal behavior of PCM. A review
65 of the different models was performed by Al-Saadi et al. in [21]. According to this study, one of the most
66 used and validated model is the finite difference algorithm. Most of the software that uses the finite
67 difference algorithm has been validated to appropriately use the model. In this sense, the most advanced
68 and well validated software that uses the finite difference algorithm is EnergyPlus which called the model
69 as CondFD. Some of the studies mentioned in the review have pointed out that to accurately predict the
70 behavior of PCM with EnergyPlus it is necessary to have an actual weather data [22] and take into account
71 the sensitive behavior of a simulation due to parameters like air infiltration and internal thermal loads and
72 occupancy schedules [23]. Furthermore, there are other studies that presented a good agreement between
73 the simulated and measured data [24, 25]. However, it has to be mentioned that before 2012 the EnergyPlus
74 CondFD model gave some unreasonable results related with the heat flux and temperature distribution in
75 horizontal placements as stated by Shresta et al. [26]. For these reason, the EnergyPlus team developed
76 several studies with the purpose of debugging the CondFD model based on experimental validation taking
77 into account the ASHRAE 140 Standard [27, 28]. After 2012, EnergyPlus released the version 7 of the
78 software that currently includes the validated CondFD model. More recently, Lee et al. performed a
79 verification of the CondFD model in version 8 against measured data [29]. The results demonstrated a
80 maximum difference between the real and simulated results of less than 5%, which lead to the conclusion
81 that the performance of PCM could be accurately predicted by the CondFD algorithm. More recent studies
82 have highlighted the debilities of the CondFD model when assessing active systems such as a radiant floor
83 [30]. The main concern when assessing these systems is that the model does not take into account the two-
84 dimensional effect of heat conduction. However, for passive application of PCM, the CondFD model has
85 been well validated as mention before. Even, a more recently study of pointed out that although the CondFD
86 model needs a revision on the associated simulation schemes for more accurate and less time consuming

87 approaches, it shows a good agreement with EnergyPlus results for exterior and interior wall surfaces [31].
88 Therefore, the CondFD model of EnergyPlus is one of the most advanced and accurate software tools to
89 appropriately assess the passive application of PCM in buildings. In this sense, there are several studies that
90 have assessed the thermal performance of PCM through BES. Tokuç et al. [32], performed an experimental
91 and numerical investigation on the use of PCM in building roof in Istanbul. Other studies like the one
92 performed by Castilho et al [33] and Vautherol et al. [34], have performed BES in a school building and
93 dwellings respectively, in order to assess the capabilities of PCM in reducing energy requirements. Finally,
94 Rastogi et al. [15] compared the results of the MCDM method with the ones obtained with EnergyPlus
95 concluding that MCDM method could be used to accurately select PCM to be applied in buildings.

96 Nevertheless, the aforementioned studies have ignored the effect of environmental conditions in
97 the thermal performance of PCM whether they use MCDM methods or Building Energy Simulations (BES)
98 as assessment tool. Given this considerations, this study aims to contrast the performance between MCDM
99 and BES for the selection of PCM wallboards for buildings. In this study, three preferences ranking-based
100 MCDM were developed to choose the best PCM alternative. For these methods, a list of all the possible
101 choices from the best to the worst suitable materials were obtained taking in consideration different material
102 selection criteria. In addition, BES are performed to assess the thermal performance and estimate the energy
103 savings of a social dwelling with the incorporation of the PCMs as wallboards. The simulation was
104 performed in three different climatic macro-zones of Ecuador where accurate meteorological data were
105 available. Finally, a comparison between the MCDM and simulation methods was performed to further
106 contrast the ranking obtained in this study.

107

108 **2. Materials and Methods**

109 **2.1. Definition of the decision making problem for material selection**

110 A phase change material (PCM) is a substance with a high heat of fusion which, melting and
111 solidifying at a certain temperature, is capable of storing and releasing large amounts of energy. Heat is
112 absorbed or released when the material changes from solid to liquid and vice versa; thus, PCMs are
113 classified as latent heat storage (LHS) units. The energy used to alter the phase of the material, given that
114 the phase change temperature should be around the desired comfort room temperature and it should lead to
115 a more stable and comfortable indoor climate [35]. For the material selection of PCM to use in buildings

116 for HVAC, the PCM must possess certain desirable thermos-physical, kinetic, chemical, economic and
117 environmental properties which are the following [6-15], [35]:

-
- 118 • High heat of fusion per unit volume and unit weight, and high specific heat. This is desirable to
119 gain more effect from latent heat storage with a small as possible volume of PCMs.
 - 120 • Phase change temperature suitably matched to the application. To gain the most out of PCMs, the
121 phase change temperature must be in accordance with the climate, location in the building or the
122 type of system where the PCM is used.
 - 123 • Chemical stability and low corrosion rate.
 - 124 • Harmless or nontoxic during fire or if the encapsulation is ruptured during regular use.
 - 125 • Reproducible crystallization without degradation.
 - 126 • Small volume changes during solidification to avoid a collapse in the structure.
 - 127 • High thermal conductivity to assist in charging and discharging of PCM within the limited time
128 frame
 - 129 • Use materials that are abundant and cheap is desired to provide a competitive advantage among
130 manufacturers.

131 In order to meet all these requirements, the most important properties to consider are the heat of
132 fusion (enthalpy difference) (Δh) and specific heat (C_p). High values are desired to keep the maximum
133 quantity of energy and minimize the thickness of the walls. High thermal conductivity (k) to disperse heat
134 through more rapidly. Low costs (C) are desired to provide a competitive advantage among manufacturers.
135 The demanded melting temperature (T_m) allows the storage unit to operate in a desirable interval of working
136 temperatures. Density (ρ) is important to reduce the thickness of the walls.

137 Given this consideration, nine alternatives of PCM are assessed in this study: GR25, RT25–RT30,
138 n-Octadecane, $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, BioPCM-Q21, BioPCM-Q23, BioPCM-Q25, BioPCM-Q27, BioPCM-Q29.
139 The properties of the alternatives with their quantitative data are given in Table 1.

140

Table 1 Material properties for the alternatives of PCM in buildings [6-14], [25].

Material	Heat of fusion [$\frac{kJ}{kg}$] (Δh)	Melting temp [°C] (T_m)	Specific heat capacity in solid state, [$\frac{kJ}{kg \cdot K}$] (Cp_s)	Specific heat capacity, [$\frac{kJ}{kg \cdot K}$] (Cp_l)	Thermal conductivity in solid state [$\frac{W}{mK}$] (k_s)	Thermal conductivity in liquid state [$\frac{W}{mK}$] (k_l)	Density in solid state [$\frac{kg}{m^3}$] (ρ_s)
GR25 (1)	45,3	23,5	1,2	1,1	1,2	1	1310
RT25–RT30 (2)	232	26,6	1,41	1,8	0,19	0,18	785
n-Octadecane(3)	243,5	27,7	2,14	2,66	0,19	0,148	865
CaCl ₂ -6H ₂ O (4)	187	29,9	1,4	2,2	1,09	0,53	1710
BioPCM-Q21 (5)	225,6	21	2,73	0,83	0,21	0,19	235
BioPCM-Q23 (6)	245,5	23	1,822	0,65	0,21	0,19	235
BioPCM-Q25 (7)	236,9	25	1,813	1,031	0,21	0,19	235
BioPCM-Q27 (8)	251,3	27	1,77	0,99	0,21	0,19	235
BioPCM-Q29 (9)	260,7	29	2,22	0,271	0,21	0,19	235

142

143 **2.2 Multi-criteria decision making methods**144 **2.2.1 Criteria weighting**

145 The criteria weights are calculated using AHP and Entropy methods combined. This methodology
146 permits to take into account the subjective and objective weights of the criteria and to obtain more
147 reasonable weight coefficients. The synthesis weight for the j th criteria is:

$$148 \quad w_j = \frac{\alpha_j \times \beta_j}{\sum_{j=1}^n \alpha_j \times \beta_j} \quad j = 1, \dots, n \quad (1)$$

149 where α_j is the weight of j th criteria obtained via AHP method, and β_j is the weight of j th criteria obtained
150 through Entropy method.

151 **a) Analytic hierarchy process (AHP)**

152 The AHP method was developed by Saaty [19] in the 1970s and has been broadly investigated
153 since then. The AHP provides a comprehensive and rational framework for structuring a problem, for
154 representing and quantifying its elements, for relating those elements to overall goals, and evaluate the
155 alternative solutions. In this research the AHP method issued to calculate the weights. AHP method steps
156 can be seen in Appendix 1 a).

157

158 **b) Entropy method**

159 Entropy method indicates that a broad distribution represents more uncertainty than that of a
160 sharply peaked one [36]. The Entropy method steps are shown in Appendix 1 b).

161 **2.2.2 COPRAS-G method**

162 COPRAS-G method [37] is a MCDM method that applies gray numbers to evaluate several
163 alternatives of an engineering application. The gray numbers are a section of the gray theory to confront
164 insufficient or incomplete information [37]. The COPRAS-G method uses a stepwise ranking and an
165 evaluating procedure of the alternatives in terms of significance and utility degree. The procedure of
166 applying COPRAS-G method is formulated in Appendix 1 c).

167

168 **2.2.3 TOPSIS method**

169 The TOPSIS method is a method to sort preferences by similarity to the ideal solution [38].
170 TOPSIS is a multiple criteria method to identify solutions from a finite set of alternatives. The basic
171 principle is that the chosen alternative should have the shortest distance from the positive ideal solution and
172 the farthest distance from the negative ideal solution. TOPSIS method steps can be seen in Appendix 1 d).

173

174 **2.2.4 VIKOR method**

175 VIKOR method solve problems of decision alternatives and criteria, assuming that compromise is
176 acceptable for conflict resolution, the decision maker wants a solution that is the closest to the ideal, and
177 the alternatives are evaluated according to all established criteria [7-8]. VIKOR ranks alternatives and
178 determines the solution named compromise that is the closest to the ideal. VIKOR method is showed in
179 Appendix 1 f).

180

181 **2.2.5 Spearman's rank correlation coefficient**

182 The Spearman's rank correlation coefficient measures the relation among nonlinear datasets. Its
183 purpose is to quantify the strength of linear relationship between variables. If there are no repeated data
184 values, a perfect Spearman correlation of +1 or -1 occurs when each of the variables is a perfect monotone
185 function of the other [39]. The Spearman's rank correlation is computed by equation (2).

186
$$R_s = 1 - \frac{6 \sum d_i^2}{n(n^2-1)} \quad (2)$$

187 Where R_s is the Spearman's rank coefficient; d_i is the difference between ranks of each case and
188 n is the Number of pairs of values.

189

190 **2.3 Simulation methodology**

191 Building energy simulations are performed to further contrast the obtained ranking with MCDM
192 method and assess the thermal performance and the energy savings that PCM can achieve.

193 To perform the BES, EnergyPlus has been used as the calculation engine with the graphic user
194 interface (GUI) – DesignBuilder. Regularly, the software uses the Transient Heat Conduction – CTF
195 method to perform the simulations, which uses a single linear equation with constants coefficients to
196 simplify the calculation of a multi-layered construction. However, this simplification is inappropriate when
197 using PCM because it ignores the variation of the enthalpy with the temperature. Hence, Tindale [40]
198 recommends using the Conduction Finite Difference (CondFD) algorithm that calculates the temperature-
199 enthalpy function to fluctuate the specific heat capacity of the material in each iteration [33]. Moreover, a
200 minimum of 12 time-steps per hour (30 in the present study) alongside the fully implicit first order
201 difference scheme should be used for the numerical simulation. As mention in the literature review
202 performed in the introduction, the CondFD model is one of the most advanced and validated algorithms to
203 assess PCM in buildings.

204 On the other hand, since the simulation entirely depends on the definition of the temperature-
205 enthalpy function, utter attention must be taken to properly define the enthalpy-temperature curve in
206 DesignBuilder to accurately assess the performance of PCM [33] Therefore, the Equation (2) is used to
207 calculate the points of the enthalpy-temperature curve for every PCM described in Table I.

$$208 \qquad \qquad \qquad \Delta h = C_p * \Delta T \qquad \qquad \qquad (2)$$

209 Where Δh is the heat of fusion (enthalpy difference), (C_p) the specific heat for solid or liquid state
210 and ΔT is the temperature difference. The properties used in the Equation 2 are melting temperature, heat
211 of fusion and specific heat capacity (Table I). For each material, the points of the enthalpy-temperature
212 curve where obtained in three sections: (a) Solid state, where the Eq. (1) is used to define the enthalpy at
213 the melting temperature using the (C_p) at solid state and considering that enthalpy is zero when the
214 temperature is zero. (b) Liquid state, where the Eq. (1) is used to define the temperature at the heat of fusion

215 when the material entirely becomes liquid. (c) During the phase change, a variation of 2°C from the melting
216 point to the heat of fusion temperature is assumed.

217

218 **2.4 Simulation cases**

219 The aim of the simulation is to numerically assess the thermal behavior and estimate the energy
220 consumption of a social dwelling with the incorporation of PCM in wallboards and rooftops in three
221 different climatic macro-zones of Ecuador of which there are accurate meteorological data. Ecuador has
222 three macro-zones which are Coast, Highlands and Amazon regions as can be seen in Figure 1. These
223 macro-zones present different climatic conditions that are controlled by the height above sea level of each
224 region. The Coast region has a rainy and a dry season, with mean temperatures that oscillates between 36
225 and 23°C, respectively. The highland region has a rainy-cold and a dry season with mean daily temperatures
226 between 13 and 18°C respectively [41]. The amazon region presents rains throughout the year and its mean
227 temperature is 25°C.

228 The relative humidity in each region varies according to the topography, which generates several
229 microclimates. Therefore, is not possible to standardize a relative humidity for each region. For this reason,
230 three cities that represent each climatic macro-zone of Ecuador are chosen for this study. These cities are
231 (a) Quito for the Highland region with a cold and semi-humid weather (Figure 1-a), (b) Guayaquil for the
232 Coast region with a warm and humid weather (Figure 1-b), and (c) Francisco de Orellana for the Amazon
233 region with a warm and very humid weather. (Figure 1-c).

234 It has to be mentioned that in Ecuador, the hourly temperature oscillation is more representative
235 than the daily or monthly oscillation. For instance, in Quito the hourly oscillation is around 9°C whereas
236 the daily and monthly temperature oscillation is 4 and 1.5°C respectively. This behavior is similar in all the
237 climatic zones of Ecuador. Therefore, the results described in this study will be considered as the mean
238 value of the hourly data represented in one day as in Figure 2. The minimum, maximum and mean
239 temperatures, relative humidity and global radiation are presented in Appendix 2

Figure 1. Representative cities for each climatic macro-zone Coast, Highlands and Amazon of Ecuador. Quito for the Highland region with a cold and semi-humid weather, Guayaquil for the Coast region with a warm and humid weather and c) Francisco de Orellana for the Amazon region with a warm and very humid weather. On the right, distribution of the outdoor temperature and relative humidity in the different cities for a typical day

240

241 The reference building is a generic social dwelling designed by the Ministry of Urban
 242 Development and Housing (MIDUVI) of Ecuador, which is given to the beneficiaries of the housing
 243 allowance. The social dwelling is designed to shelter four people in a space of 36 m² (Appendix 3) which
 244 represents an occupancy density of 0.111 people/m². For simulation purposes, this occupancy density is
 245 considered as continuous throughout the day and night generating an internal thermal gain of 4 W/m²
 246 including lighting and equipment [42] To simplify the calculation, a single zone is considered in the
 247 simulation.

248 On the other hand, despite the different climatic macro-zones of Ecuador, this dwelling has been
 249 built in every zone of the country, with the same construction materials (concrete for walls and metal sheet
 250 roofing). Depending on the region, the materials selection as well as the design has been performed
 251 neglecting the effects of the environment conditions. Referring to the materials, they do not prevent the
 252 building for radiation heat gains in the warmest regions. In addition, solar protection systems were not
 253 considered from the design perspective. In contrast, the material does not keep the internal heat gains during
 254 night which is important in the coldest regions. Consequently, as demonstrated by several researches, the
 255 conditions within the building are inappropriate to ensure healthy [43] and comfortable conditions inside
 256 the building [44] with the additional shortcoming of being energetically inefficient [45].

257 For this reason, the present study has the additional purpose of suggest an improvement to these
 258 buildings by using PCM on the wallboards (Appendix 4). The envelope materials improvement is only
 259 considered for the walls and roof, because, those elements of the buildings present the highest thermal gains
 260 and losses during the day [46]. With these configurations, the thermal resistance for the envelope materials
 261 is presented in Appendix 5.

262 Four different tests are performed in order to assess the thermal performance of the PCM through BES: (a)
 263 an operative temperature distribution on one year span, (b) a comparison between the outdoor and the indoor
 264 operative temperature, (c) an energy balance of the envelope materials and (d) a comparison between the
 265 inner and outer surfaces temperatures. These analyses are performed by comparing the reference case with
 266 the improved case.

267 In addition, to contrast the obtained ranking with the MCDM method, a comparison between the
 268 estimated energy savings achieved by the PCM in the different regions of Ecuador is calculated using the
 269 Equation 4 [47]. This equation compares the energy consumption between a reference case and the
 270 improved cases. Thus, an HVAC system is included in the simulations to obtain a result of the annual
 271 energy demand for every case. However, for the simulation to be comparable, a preliminary parametric
 272 simulation is conducted to determine the temperature and relative humidity set points that obtain zero
 273 discomfort hours for all regions (Table 2). This analysis demonstrated that heating, cooling as well as a
 274 dehumidification systems are needed in Quito to assure zero discomfort hours due to the temperature
 275 variation between day and night (i.e. approximately 9°C). In contrast, in the warm and humid climate of
 276 Guayaquil and Francisco de Orellana, there is only need of cooling and dehumidification due to its elevated
 277 temperature and relative humidity during day and night. It is important to mention that the improvement
 278 percentage resulting from the heating and cooling demand simulation are an estimation of the relative
 279 behavior of each PCM.

$$280 \quad \textit{Improvement percentage} = 100 * \frac{\textit{Reference case consumption} - \textit{Improved cases consumption}}{\textit{Reference case consumption}} \quad (4)$$

281

Table 2. HVAC system set-points that ensure zero discomfort hours for the cities of Quito, Guayaquil and Francisco de Orellana

	Heating [°C]	Cooling [°C]	Relative humidity [%]
Quito	20,5	26,0	35,0
Guayaquil	-	26,0	45,0
Francisco de Orellana	-	26,0	45,0

282 **3. Results**

283 **3.1 Results MCDM**

284 **3.1.1 Criteria weighting**

285 To obtain the criteria weighting, the comparison among properties has been performed for every
286 alternative as showed in Table I. The properties identification appears as (Δh) , (T_m) , (Cp_s) , (Cp_l) , (k_s) , (k_l) ,
287 and (ρ_s) . The criteria weighting was firstly performed by the AHP method to obtain the subjective weights
288 of different evaluation criteria. After the decision hierarchy for the problem was designed, the criteria were
289 compared pairwise based on the experience of the authors. Appendix 6 shows the scale of relative
290 importance used in the AHP method.

291 The comparison among criteria for balanced scales AHP method is shown in Appendix 7. The
292 most important criteria to generate the matrix was considered (Δh) ; moderate less important was considered
293 (T_m) , (Cp_s) , (Cp_l) , (k_s) and (k_l) ; extremely less important was taken (ρ_s) . The value of the consistency
294 index ($CI=0,010$) and the consistency ratio ($CR=0,009$), which are lower than the limit of 0.1, indicate that
295 the results are consistent. Furthermore, the decision matrix generated for a PCM in buildings which take
296 into account the importance of each criteria are illustrated in Appendix 8. At the final step, the compromised
297 weights of the criteria (w_j) were calculated using the Eq. (1). In Appendix 9, the weight coefficient of every
298 criterion was determined based on the results of AHP and Entropy methods. On one hand, the most
299 representative values were (Δh) 44 %, (T_m) 19.1 % and (Cp_s) 17.8 %. On the other hand, 19.1 % of the
300 overall weight is distributed in (Cp_l) , (k_s) , (k_l) , and (ρ_s) .

301

302 **3.1.2 COPRAS-G method**

303 The related decision matrix is first developed from the gray numbers applied in COPRAS-G as
304 illustrated in Appendix 10. The normalized matrix made of gray numbers for the COPRAS-G method is
305 shown in Appendix 11. Appendix 12 shows the priority values (Q_i) and quantitative utility (U_i) values for
306 the candidate alternatives of the PCM for buildings and the ranking of the alternative material of the method
307 as 3-8-9-5-6-7-4-2-1. For this results n-Octadecane and BioPCM-Q27 obtained the first and second ranks
308 respectively, in contrast GR25 resulted to be the worst choice.

309 3.1.3 TOPSIS method

310 The decision matrix given in Table I was normalized for the application of the TOPSIS method
311 and this was multiplied by the obtained compromised weights. The weighted and normalized decision
312 matrix V_{ij} for the material alternatives of a PCM for buildings are illustrated in Appendix 13. The ideal and
313 nadir ideal solutions are presented in Appendix 14. The distances from the ideal (S_i^+) and nadir ideal
314 solutions (S_i^-), the relative closeness to the ideal solution (C_i) and the ranking is shown in Appendix 15.
315 The rankings of the alternative materials are 3-8-5-7-2-6-9-4-1. For TOPSIS method, n-Octadecane and
316 BioPCM-Q27 obtained the first and second ranks PCM in buildings. GR25 has the last rank and RT25-
317 RT30 is the second to last rank.

318

319 3.1.4 VIKOR method

320 The values of E_i , F_i and P_i were calculated as shown in Appendix 16. The material with the lowest P_i value
321 was given the best rank. According to the ranking of alternatives by the VIKOR method presented in
322 Appendix 16, the ranking materials for a PCM for buildings is 9-3-8-4-2-7-6-5-1 which indicates that
323 BioPCM-Q29 and n-Octadecane obtain the first and second ranks for the PCM for buildings. On the other
324 hand, GR25 has the last rank and PCM-Q25 is the second last rank.

325

326 3.2 Simulation results

327 In order to understand the effect of the climate conditions in the thermal behavior of the PCM,
328 four tests were performed for all PCM in the present study. The results showed that every material presented
329 an improvement compared with the reference case. However, only the results of the RT25-RT30 PCM are
330 presented in this paper as sample material due to its superior performance.

331

332 3.2.1 Indoor operative temperature distribution

333 The indoor operative temperature distribution test was performed to compare the indoor thermal
334 behavior between the reference and the improved case. In Quito and Francisco de Orellana there is a
335 scattered distribution of the operative temperatures with no significant differences between the reference
336 and PCM case as shown in the Appendix 17. Conversely, in Guayaquil the PCM material clearly maintains

337 the majority of the hours below 30°C while the reference case is always above this figure. This is related
338 with the high solar radiation in Guayaquil where the metal roofing system is ineffective to protect the
339 building from the solar heat gains.

340

341 **3.2.2 Comparison between indoor and outdoor temperature**

342 This test was performed to contrast the variation of outdoor and indoor temperature for the
343 reference and PCM cases on an hourly basis. It is notable that the temperature fluctuation between day and
344 night is elevated in Quito and Guayaquil (i.e. 7°C). On the contrary, in Francisco de Orellana the
345 temperature difference between day and night is only about 5°C (Appendix 18). This behavior is evident in
346 the reference case where the indoor temperature follows the distribution of the outdoor temperature.
347 Contrariwise, the PCM case maintains a uniform distribution during the day which in some cases acts as a
348 detrimental side effect. In Guayaquil for instance, the PCM material maintains the indoor temperature
349 around 28°C whereas the reference case maintains it 1°C less during the morning. During the afternoon
350 when the outdoor temperature reaches its highest peak, the PCM material maintains the temperature 2°C
351 below the one obtained by the reference case.

352

353 **3.2.3 Envelope energy balance**

354 The envelope energy balance test shows the energy gains and losses of the envelope to comprehend the
355 thermal performance of the PCM as wallboard compared with the reference case material. In Quito there is
356 no difference between the energy balance of the PCM and the reference case. On the contrary, in Guayaquil
357 and Francisco de Orellana the figures show that there are less energy losses from 1:00 to 11:00 with the
358 PCM in the wall as demonstrated in Appendix 19. Nevertheless, as discussed before this behavior is
359 inappropriate for this kind of climate since more energy losses through the envelope are preferable to
360 maintain a comfortable temperature within the building. Further, the PCM does not allow as much energy
361 gains as the reference case during the afternoon which is desirable since this is the critical period of time.

362 **3.2.4 Inner and outer surface temperatures**

363 To utterly understand the effect of the climate conditions in the performance of the PCM materials,
364 the energy balance test is complemented with the inner and outer surface temperatures of the reference and
365 the PCM case (Appendix 20)

366 Assessing the walls and roof in Quito, is immediately clear that the walls are a key element where
367 the PCM can improve the thermal behavior of the envelope. During the night, the PCM maintains an inner
368 surface temperature 2°C higher than the outer surface which will lead to a better comfort sensation due to
369 the radiant temperature of the wall. During the day, when the operative temperature could reach discomfort
370 ranges, the PCM maintains the inner surface temperature lower temperature than the outer surface.
371 However, the differences between the temperature of the inner surface with and without PCM are less than
372 1°C.

373 On the contrary, in Guayaquil and Francisco de Orellana the inner and outer surface temperature
374 differences between the reference and the PCM are more notable. The inner surface temperature using PCM
375 is nearly constant during the day and night. Then again, this demonstrates a possible problem within the
376 building since the thermal sensation of a warm wall could cause discomfort. During night, thermal losses
377 throughout the envelope are preferable, so in the morning the inner surface generates a cool thermal
378 sensation. Nonetheless, this effect is diminished because the inner surface temperature is higher than the
379 outer surface. On the contrary, the PCM has a positive outcome during the day since the inner temperature
380 is lower than the outer temperature.

381

382 **4 Discussion**

383 The building sector contributes up to 30% of global annual greenhouse gas emissions and
384 consumes up to 40% of all energy [1-2]. Therefore, if targets for greenhouse gas emissions reduction are to
385 be met, it is clear that decision-makers must tackle emissions from the building sector. In this regards PCM
386 appears as one of the key element to reduce energy usage and greenhouse gas emissions in buildings.

387 This study developed MCDM methods and BES to assess the suitability of developing PCM for
388 building wallboards in Ecuador. In doing so, it contributes towards the literature surrounding MCDM and
389 BES studies with the novelty and added credibility of the use of expert validation. It is the first specific
390 study to assess effect of the environment on the PCM selection. This approach can aid decision makers in

391 moving towards to a regulation policy which improves the energy savings in Ecuadorian buildings between
 392 10-25% as is given in Figure 2. The method could also be applied more widely with appropriate adaptation,
 393 so could contribute for energy efficiency in buildings around the world.

394 MCDM are an important tool to recognize and identify the best alternative in a bunch of several
 395 of them. These methods can adapt to different sort of environments and conditions that would affect the
 396 final result and that is why these approaches are applied in different areas of science, engineering and
 397 management [19, 20]. The adoption of several MCDM and the correlation between the results shown as
 398 MCDM has a powerful tool for material selection [19, 20].

Figure 2. Improvement percentage of the PCM materials for the cities of Quito, Francisco de Orellana y Guayaquil.

399 In this case, we take advantage of MCDM in order to know the best alternative for the use of PCM
 400 in buildings. Figure 3 shows the overall rank of each MCDM for the different material alternatives.
 401 According to the MCDM COPRAS-G, VIKOR, and TOPSIS, the best material alternatives are n-
 402 Octadecane and BioPCM-Q29, because they have highest values of the most important properties for a
 403 PCM for buildings. They have a high heat of fusion (Δh) 44 %, low melting temperature (T_m) 19,1 % and
 404 high specific heat capacity in solid state (Cp_s) 17,8%. In addition, GR25 was presented on the last rank
 405 alternatives for this three MCDMs.

406

407 **Figure 3.** Rank materials vs. alternative Material for a PCM in buildings. The value of 1 indicate the best
 408 material alternative, meanwhile 9 indicate the last rank alternative.

409 The Spearman's correlation coefficients for a PCM for buildings are presented in table3. This table
 410 represent the substantial agreement among MCDM methods. The magnitude of this parameter for a PCM
 411 exceeds 0,59 for the relation of COPRAS-G, TOPSIS and VIKOR. Moreover, the correlation has a value
 412 of 0,7 between TOPSIS and the other two methods.

413

414 **Table 3.** Spearman's correlation indexes

	TOPSIS	COPRAS-G
VIKOR	0,700	0,592
COPRAS-G	0,700	-

415

416 In order to contrast the obtained ranking with the MCDM method, a BES was performed
 417 considering the social dwelling as conditioned. In addition, this analysis is used to establish the phase
 418 change material that obtained the highest energy savings in every climatic macro-zone of Ecuador. As
 419 shown in Figure 13; **Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.**, RT25-RT30 is the material that
 420 achieved the greatest energy savings compared with the reference case for Guayaquil and Francisco de
 421 Orellana. However, compared with the MCDM method, this material is ranked between 5 and 8.

422 On the other hand, all PCM resulted in good energy savings in Quito (around 25% of
 423 improvement), except for GR25 and CaCl₂-6H₂O. The GR25 PCM has the lower improvement percentage
 424 in every climatic zone, which is directly related with the ranking obtained with the MCDM method. On the

425 contrary, the n-Octadecane which is ranked first in the MCDM method is not the best material according
426 to the simulation results.

427 The discrepancies between the MCDM and the simulation method demonstrate the importance
428 that the environment variables plays to appropriately assess the performance of PCM. In addition, these
429 results are explained by the thermal behavior assessment previously made in this study. For example, in a
430 warm and humid place, using PCM during night is rather detrimental because the dwelling cannot evacuate
431 all the heat gained during the day, which generate a higher demand of refrigeration. These kinds of
432 considerations are overlooked when evaluating PCM with the MCDM method, which generates the
433 discrepancies in the results.

434

435 **4.1 Literature comparison**

436 The overriding consensus in the researches that uses MCDM method to select PCM performed by
437 Fernández et al., [7] and Khare et al., [8], is that PCM should have a high heat of fusion (Δh), an adequate
438 melting temperature and high specific heat capacity in solid state (Cp_s) and liquid state (Cp_l). In either case,
439 environmental or operational conditions have been overlooked.

440 Rastogi et al., [15] developed a selection of materials in PCM for HVAC using figures of merit to
441 numerically identify the relative performance of participating candidates. Furthermore, they used TOPSIS
442 method for the selection of a list of alternatives. The principal criteria for the material selection were the
443 phase change temperature, density, heat of fusion, specific heat capacity and thermal conductivity. In
444 addition, the top ranked PCMs were selected for a simulation study using open source software PCMs
445 Express based on finite difference mathematical model and enthalpy method for simulation.

446 In case of Rastogi et al., [15] the simulation was executed for an unconditioned building in a span of
447 a year (8670 h), as is in our study. To maintain the human comfort temperature (21–26 °C), a conventional
448 system of brick masonry walls, concrete cement roof and ceiling compared with the PCM was used,
449 whereas, in our study we assessed the performance of a conventional brick masonry for walls and a metal
450 roofing sheet improved with PCM in three different climatic macro-zones of Ecuador. The thickness of
451 each wallboard is considered to be 15 mm, while we considered a 10 cm brick with a 1 cm PCM for the
452 wallboard and roof. The other boundary conditions being the night ventilation, window in outer wall
453 (occupying 40% area of the total wall) and equivalent radiator output of 50 W/m². In our study, we consider
454 natural ventilation in the unconditioned case and a HVAC and dehumidification systems for the conditioned

455 case in every climatic macro-zone. Furthermore, 10% of window to wall ratio was used as the reference
456 case and the internal gains value was considered as a typical dwelling (4 W/m²).

457 Even though the results of Rastogi et al., [15] showed a good agreement between the MCDM and
458 simulations methods, it did not take into account the effect of the environment to assess the performance of
459 PCM. In fact, there is no clear information about the climate conditions surrounding the assessed building.
460 However, taking into account that they only analyses the operative temperature of an air-conditioned
461 building, the results are similar to the ones obtained in Quito in the present study. This means that the
462 thermal performance is appropriate for the entire day in cold and semi-humid climates.

463 Nevertheless, as demonstrated in the present study, in warm climates, PCM could perform
464 inappropriately during night. This fact demonstrates the discrepancies between both methods. Furthermore,
465 it proves the importance of assessing the impact of the environmental variables in the evaluation of PCM.

466 Likewise, other studies have performed BES in order to assess the performance of PCM. Castilho et
467 al. [33] evaluated PCM in a school building with large thermal gains due to computational equipment (i.e.
468 28 W/m²). The PCM was incorporated in the roof and walls of the rooms as in our study. Moreover, they
469 performed the assessment considering the rooms with and without HVAC systems. Although, they
470 performed an hourly assessment of the indoor temperature performance, they neglected the effect of the
471 surface temperature and the thermal gains and losses of the wallboards. In our study, these parameters are
472 claimed to have an impact on the thermal perception of the occupants. On the other hand, Vautherot et al.
473 [34] performed BES to assess the energy requirements and discomfort hours by using different PCM in a
474 dwelling. They compare the energy requirements for the HVAC system with the discomfort hours
475 associated with every PCM, whereas we compared the energy requirements achieving zero discomfort
476 hours in order to the simulation to be comparable. Furthermore, they overpass the fact that the hourly
477 variation of the indoor temperature affects the thermal comfort of the occupants. However, our simulation
478 results are in some level of agreement with those obtained by them regarding the fact that the appropriate
479 selection of HVAC system's set points affects the thermal performance of the PCM.

480 Air infiltration through the building envelope has a significant impact on the space heating energy
481 use in buildings [10]. Energy simulation tools can be used to determine the impact of air infiltration through
482 the building envelope. Although there are very detailed and complex approaches available to model air
483 infiltration using air flow networks (AFN) and computation fluid dynamics (CFD), typically building
484 energy simulation tools use a simplified approach to estimate air change rate based on building air tightness

485 measured by pressurization tests [15]. Several field surveys and test methods have been developed to
486 specify building level air infiltration rates for a known standard pressure difference across the envelope. In
487 an effort to specify air-barrier requirements, the ASHRAE 90.1 Envelope Subcommittee has developed a
488 list of component infiltration rates that can be used to calculate the overall building air infiltration rate. In
489 this case, air flow has been considered fixed infiltration value of air renovation in the simulation set.
490 Although, climatic parameters have been taken into account for the simulation. A more realistic simulation
491 could be conducted in the near future for the coast and Amazonian air infiltration cases.

492 Finally, several studies about the lifetime of the PCMs has been performed [6, 15]. The lifetime of
493 the systems under investigation; 50, 75, or 100 years which is expected for the case of BioPCMs.

494 To determine quantities required in the building, the general rule is 1.5 of BioPCM™ per cubic meter
495 (m³) of interior space. In this, research a simple economic analysis for the BioPCMs application in
496 Buildings should be take into account 36m² floor space x 2.2 high ceiling = 79.2 m³. In this case, the
497 quantity of BioPCMs is about 118.8 kg of material, which have a price of 4158 \$. This information appears
498 on the website of BioPCMs.

499

500 **5 Conclusions and recommendations**

501 In this paper the material selection problem for a PCM for buildings was solved utilizing a decision
502 model. The model includes the COPRAS-G, OCRA, ARAS, VIKOR and TOPSIS methods. According to
503 the results of COPRAS, VIKOR and TOPSIS methods, the best choices were n-Octadecane and BioPCM-
504 Q29, because they have highest values of the most important criteria for a PCM for wallboards in buildings.

505 The BES were carried out to contrast the results of the MCDM method which led to the conclusion
506 that a thermal assessment of the PCM is necessary to better understand the behavior of the materials during
507 the operation with the effect of the environmental conditions as well as the indoor conditions. This fact is
508 clearly demonstrated by the simulation results. Depending on the climate conditions, PCM has different
509 thermal behavior that could be an improvement in some cases and disadvantageous in others. For this
510 reason, an extensive assessment of the climate condition should be made before actually apply this strategy
511 in unconditioned buildings.

512 In addition, PCM present a good thermal behavior during day and night in cold places, especially at
513 night, when the PCM maintain the indoor temperature on a constant comfortable temperature. Furthermore,

514 the inner surface temperature provides a warm thermal sensation due to the radiant effect of the wall. On
515 the other hand, the thermal performance during day and night is different in warm and humid places. During
516 the day, the PCM prevents the heat evacuation of the building which in fact generates a warmer space
517 compared with the reference building. Overnight, the PCM does not allow the inner surface to cool down,
518 which generates a warmer wall than the reference case that could cause discomfort. Nevertheless, PCM
519 present a good performance during afternoon keeping the indoor temperature below the outdoor
520 temperature. For these reasons, in the case of unconditioned buildings, PCM are preferable to be installed
521 in buildings located in cold places since it has a good performance throughout the entire day. For
522 unconditioned buildings located in warm places, PCM has a better performance during afternoon. On the
523 other hand, if social dwellings were designed to use HVAC systems, it is clear that PCM could represent
524 an improvement in all climatic macro zones of Ecuador. In this sense, the RT25-RT30 PCM has the better
525 performance among all assessed PCM in this study.

526 Furthermore, this methodology could also be used with appropriate adaptation to other places of the
527 world and it could contribute for energy efficiency and greenhouse mitigation in buildings around the world.

528 Finally, in relation with the MCDM it is necessary to find an environmental variable that can fulfill
529 a correlation with the BES model.

530

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537

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652 **Appendix 1.** Description of a) AHP method algorithm, b) Entropy method algorithm, c) COPRAS-G
 653 method algorithm, d) TOPSIS method algorithm, f) VIKOR method algorithm.
 654

655 **Appendix 2.** Weather variables (temperature, relative humidity and radiation) for the simulation cities
 656 of highlands-Quito, Coast- Guayaquil and Amazon – Francisco de Orellana

		Temperature [°C]	Relative humidity	Radiation
			[%]	
Highland - Quito	Min	4	20.0	0.0
	Max	25.7	100.0	1066.0
	Mean	13.7	74.5	115.9
Coast - Guayaquil	Min	18.9	33.0	0.0
	Max	34.4	100.0	987.0
	Mean	25.0	71.1	75.6
Amazon – Francisco de Orellana	Min	16.6	42.0	0.0
	Max	30.9	100.0	914.0
	Mean	23.2	74.6	74.0

Appendix 3. Schema of the generic Ecuadorian social dwelling designed by MIDUVI of Ecuador. The social dwelling was designed to shelter four people in a space of 36 m². The dwelling has two bedrooms, one bathroom and a kitchen-dinning-living shared room.

658

a)

b)

Reference wall (not to scale)

c)

Improved wall with PCM (not to scale)

d)

Reference roof (not to scale)

Improved roof with PCM (not to scale)

Appendix 4. Construction configuration for reference case and the improved case with the PCM a) Reference wall, b) Improved wall with PCM, c) reference roof, d) improved roof with PCM.

659

660

Appendix 5. Thermal resistance properties for wall and roof materials.

Material	Walls - U [W/m ² K]	Roof - U [W/m ² K]
Reference	2,51	6,06
GR-25	2,45	5,77
RT25-RT30	2,20	4,53
n-Octadecane	2,17	4,40
CaCl ₂ -6H ₂ O	2,41	5,50
BioPCM-Q21	3,31	4,61
BioPCM-Q23	3,31	4,65
BioPCM-Q25	3,31	4,65
BioPCM-Q27	3,31	4,65
BioPCM-Q29	3,31	4,65

661

662

Appendix 6 Scale of relative importance for the AHP method

Definition	Intensity of importance
Equal importance	1
Moderate importance	3
Strong importance	5
Very strong importance	7
Extreme importance	9
Intermediate importance	2, 4, 6, 8

663

664

Appendix 7 Comparison among criteria of materials for PCM in AHP method

(Δh)	(T_m)	(Cp_s)	(Cp_l)	(k_s)	(k_l)	(ρ_s)
1	3	3	3	3	3	9
0,333	1	1	1	1	1	7
0,333	1	1	1	1	1	7
0,333	1	1	1	1	1	7
0,333	1	1	1	1	1	7
0,333	1	1	1	1	1	7
0,111	0,143	0,143	0,143	0,143	0,143	1

665

666

Appendix 8 normalized decision matrix P_{ij} for AHP method

Material	(Δh)	(T_m)	(Cp_s)	(Cp_l)	(k_s)	(k_l)	(ρ_s)
1	0,068	0,301	0,212	0,249	0,702	0,812	0,523
2	0,346	0,341	0,249	0,407	0,111	0,146	0,313
3	0,364	0,355	0,378	0,601	0,111	0,120	0,345
4	0,279	0,383	0,247	0,497	0,638	0,430	0,682
5	0,337	0,269	0,482	0,188	0,123	0,154	0,094
6	0,367	0,295	0,322	0,147	0,123	0,154	0,094
7	0,354	0,320	0,320	0,233	0,123	0,154	0,094
8	0,375	0,346	0,312	0,224	0,123	0,154	0,094

9 0,389 0,372 0,392 0,061 0,123 0,154 0,094

667 **Appendix 9** Criteria weighting by the AHP (α_j) and balanced scales entropy (β_j), methods and
668 compromised weighting (w_j) methods.

	(Δh)	(T_m)	(Cp_s)	(Cp_l)	(k_s)	(k_l)	(ρ_s)
α_j	0,345	0,127	0,127	0,127	0,127	0,127	0,021
β_j	0,214	0,253	0,235	0,143	0,027	0,073	0,057
w_j	0,440	0,191	0,178	0,108	0,020	0,055	0,007

669
670

Appendix 10 Decision matrix of COPRAS-G method

Material	(Δh)	(T_m)	(Cp_s)	(Cp_l)	(k_s)	(k_l)	(ρ_s)
1	40,77	49,83	21,15	25,85	1,08	1,32	0,99
2	208,8	255,2	23,94	29,26	1,269	1,551	1,62
3	219,15	267,85	24,93	30,47	1,926	2,354	2,394
4	168,3	205,7	26,91	32,89	1,26	1,54	1,98
5	203,04	248,16	18,9	23,1	2,457	3,003	0,747
6	220,95	270,05	20,7	25,3	1,6398	2,0042	0,585
7	213,21	260,59	22,5	27,5	1,6317	1,9943	0,928
8	226,17	276,43	24,3	29,7	1,593	1,947	0,891
9	234,63	286,77	26,1	31,9	1,998	2,442	0,244

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Appendix 11 Normalized matrix made of gray numbers

Material	(Δh)	(T_m)	(Cp_s)	(Cp_l)	(k_s)	(k_l)	(ρ_s)
1	0,021	0,026	0,091	0,111	0,065	0,080	0,086
2	0,108	0,132	0,103	0,126	0,077	0,094	0,140
3	0,114	0,139	0,107	0,131	0,117	0,143	0,208
4	0,087	0,107	0,116	0,141	0,076	0,093	0,172
5	0,105	0,129	0,081	0,099	0,149	0,182	0,065
6	0,115	0,140	0,089	0,109	0,099	0,121	0,051
7	0,111	0,135	0,097	0,118	0,099	0,121	0,080
8	0,117	0,143	0,104	0,128	0,212	0,118	0,077
9	0,122	0,149	0,112	0,137	0,268	0,148	0,021

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Appendix 12 Pi, Ri, Qi and Ui values.

Material	Pi	Ri	Qi	Ui	Rank
1	0,060	0,023	0,089	66,303	9
2	0,090	0,024	0,117	87,534	8
3	0,107	0,025	0,134	100,000	1
4	0,095	0,029	0,117	87,713	7
5	0,094	0,018	0,131	97,535	4
6	0,087	0,020	0,120	90,036	5
7	0,088	0,021	0,119	89,202	6
8	0,102	0,023	0,131	98,224	2
9	0,104	0,024	0,131	97,818	3

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Appendix 13 Weighted and normalized decision matrix, V_{ij} of TOPSIS.

Material	(Δh)	(T_m)	(Cp_s)	(Cp_l)	(k_s)	(k_l)	(ρ_s)
1	0,030	0,058	0,038	0,027	0,014	0,045	0,004
2	0,152	0,065	0,044	0,044	0,002	0,008	0,002
3	0,160	0,068	0,067	0,065	0,002	0,007	0,002
4	0,123	0,073	0,044	0,054	0,013	0,024	0,005
5	0,148	0,052	0,086	0,020	0,002	0,009	0,001
6	0,161	0,056	0,057	0,016	0,002	0,009	0,001
7	0,156	0,061	0,057	0,025	0,002	0,009	0,001
8	0,165	0,066	0,056	0,024	0,002	0,009	0,001
9	0,171	0,071	0,070	0,007	0,002	0,009	0,001

676

Appendix 14 The ideal and nadir ideal solutions of TOPSIS method.

	(Δh)	(T_m)	(Cp_s)	(Cp_l)	(k_s)	(k_l)	(ρ_s)
V^+	0,171	0,052	0,086	0,065	0,014	0,045	0,001
V^-	0,030	0,073	0,038	0,007	0,002	0,007	0,005

677

Appendix 15 Computation details for TOPSIS method.

Material	S_i^+	S_i^-	C_i	Rank
1	0,154	0,048	0,236	9
2	0,065	0,129	0,665	5
3	0,049	0,146	0,750	1
4	0,072	0,106	0,597	8
5	0,063	0,130	0,674	3
6	0,069	0,134	0,660	6
7	0,065	0,129	0,666	4
8	0,065	0,138	0,678	2
9	0,074	0,145	0,650	7

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Appendix 16 Computation details for VIKOR method.

Material	E_i	F_i	P_i	Rank
1	0,828	0,440	1,000	9
2	0,400	0,153	0,263	5
3	0,231	0,069	0,024	2
4	0,359	0,155	0,236	4
5	0,426	0,191	0,471	8
6	0,458	0,148	0,395	7
7	0,414	0,107	0,270	6
8	0,348	0,112	0,153	3
9	0,266	0,108	0,000	1

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a) Quito

b) Guayaquil

c) Francisco de Orellana

Appendix 17. Results of the operative temperature distribution on one year span for the cities of a) Quito, b) Guayaquil and c) Francisco de Orellana

a) Quito

b) Guayaquil

c) Francisco de Orellana

Appendix 18. Comparison between indoor and outdoor temperature for the cities of a) Quito, b) Guayaquil and c) Francisco de Orellana

a) Quito

b) Guayaquil

c) Francisco de Orellana

Appendix 19. Comparison of envelope energy balance during a day between reference walls and PCM walls, reference roofs and PCM roofs, for the cities of a) Quito, b) Guayaquil and c) Francisco de Orellana

Quito-Wall

Quito-Roof

Guayaquil-Wall

Guayaquil-Roof

Francisco de Orellana-Wall

Francisco de Orellana-Roof

Appendix 20. Envelope surface temperatures